

Management pathway of blood glucose control in adult patients (≥18 years old) with COVID-19 & prescribed dexamethasone

(For pregnant women: see [section 2](#) for details on monitoring and referral pathway)

Dexamethasone is indicated? Prescribe dexamethasone using the 'dexamethasone COVID' orderset on EPR (dexamethasone 6mg po/iv once a day (morning) for 7-10 days, blood glucose monitoring, PRN Novorapid®, hypoglycaemia bundle). Check HbA1c

Use this protocol when hydrocortisone 50mg IV TDS course is prescribed. Other steroids may be used e.g. methylprednisolone and prednisolone. Use the same principles and consult the diabetes team for specific advice.

Add Humulin-I® to regular diabetes treatments as follows.

Patient already on insulin or T1DM (more details in [section 6.2](#)): KEEP USUAL INSULIN BUT ADD HUMULIN-I as follows:

- To avoid in-hospital DKA/HHS keep usual basal insulin going but ADD Humulin-I®. Examples of usual basal/background insulins: Detemir (Levemir®), Glargine (Lantus®/Abasaglar®), Degludec (Tresiba®), Glargine 300units/ml (Toujeo®), Insulatard®, Humulin-I®, or Insuman Basal®
- Stop bolus insulin (Novorapid®, Humalog®, Apidra®, Humulin-S®, Actrapid®) if patient NOT eating.

Patients on oral diabetes treatments (see [section 6.1](#); [table 2](#)): Stop metformin (AKI, eGFR <30, lactate >4mmol/L), **stop SGLT2 inhibitors** (any acutely unwell patient), **stop sulfonylureas** (e.g. gliclazide) if patient not eating or on high flow O2 (≥40%)/CPAP.

Maintain blood glucose 6-11 mmol/L

Treat as for hypoglycaemia if CBG <4 mmol/L (see Trust protocol)

Refer to the inpatient diabetes team:

- Patients admitted with DKA and/or HHS.
- Patients on dexamethasone & on Humulin-I® (this protocol).
- Patients who require education on use of insulin and/or CBG monitoring.
- If switching to a different steroids course or higher/lower doses.
- CBGs >20 or <4 mmol/L despite adjustments to treatment.
- New or alterations to enteral/parenteral feeding.
- Patients on insulin pump.
- Pregnant women with a single reading ≥10 OR >7.8mmol/L (x2) OR HbA1c ≥42mmol/mol (≥6%).

EPR referrals to inpatient diabetes teams

"Diabetes inpatient referral" @Denmark hill OR @PRUH

Bleeps:

- Denmark hill:
 - Diabetes nurses (301) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700],
 - Inpatient diabetes SPR (122) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700; Sat-Sun 1000-1800].
- PRUH: DSN (764) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700]

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For patients who need Dexamethasone as part of COVID-19 treatment

Type 'dexamethasone COVID' in EPR orders; The bundle contains Dexamethasone course (6mg po/iv od), glucose monitoring, supplemental Novorapid®, hypoglycaemia bundle. Check HbA1c

Maintain blood glucose 6-11 mmol/L; treat as for hypoglycaemia when CBG <4mmol/L

Table 1: Type 2 diabetes medications adjustments

Medication group	When to stop	When to restart
Metformin	Acute kidney injury OR eGFR ≤30 OR lactate >4 mmol/L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> eGFR improved to >30 OR AKI resolved. Then assess Lactate as part of holistic clinical assessment. If improving and lactate <4 mmol/L and renal parameters above are fulfilled then can restart Metformin.
SGLT2 inhibitors (e.g. dapagliflozin, empagliflozin, canagliflozin, sotagliflozin, ertugliflozin)	Always stop in acutely unwell patients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restart on discharge if clinically well. NOT to restart if patient presented in DKA. To add to discharge summary for GP/diabetes clinic review (if under diabetes service).
Sulfonylureas (e.g. gliclazide, glipizide, glibenclamide, glimepiride, tolbutamide)	<p>Patient not eating</p> <p>Patient on high flow oxygen (>40%) OR CPAP</p>	Clinically improving and able to eat meals.
DPP4 inhibitors (e.g. sitagliptin, saxagliptin, linagliptin)	<p>Continue unless there is acute kidney injury (sitagliptin, saxagliptin)</p> <p>OR acute liver failure (linagliptin)</p>	On resolution of acute kidney injury or acute liver failure.

Table 2: Humulin-I® doses for patients not known to have diabetes or have T2DM on oral treatments (Group A: insulin naïve)

Actual or estimated body weight (kg)	Age ≤70 years AND eGFR >30		Age >70 OR eGFR ≤30	
	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)
<45kg	Discuss insulin dosing with the diabetes team. Risk of hypoglycaemia.			
45-60 kg	9 units	5 units	4 units	2 units
61-70 kg	12 units	6 units	6 units	3 units
71-80 kg	19 units	10 units	9 units	5 units
81-100 kg	27 units	14 units	13 units	7 units
101-120 kg	33 units	17 units	17 units	9 units
>120 kg	40 units	21 units	20 units	10 units

Table 3: Added Humulin-I® doses for patients who are already on insulin or T1DM (Group B).

Step 1: Calculate insulin total daily dose (TDD) currently taken by the patient (usual insulin regimen) [units]	Step 2: Identify the characteristics of the patient and ADD Humulin-I® to their usual insulin			
	Age ≤70 years AND eGFR >30		Age >70 OR eGFR ≤30	
	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)
<30 units	5 units	3 units	3 units	0
30-50 units	6 units	3 units	3 units	2 units
50-75 units	10 units	5 units	5 units	3 units
76-100 units	15 units	8 units	8 units	4 units
>100 units	22 units	11 units	11 units	6 units

Table 4: Supplemental fast acting insulin (Novorapid®) dose based on patient's insulin total daily dose (TDD) (or weight if TDD is not known).

Capillary blood glucose threshold (mmol/L)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD) <50units/day (OR Weight <50 kg)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD) 50-100units (OR Weight 50-100 kg)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD) >100 units (OR Weight >100 kg)
	Novorapid® dose	Novorapid® dose	Novorapid® dose
11.1-14.9	2 units	4 units	5 units
15-19.9	4 units	6 units	7 units
20 or above	6 units	8 units	10 units

Figure 1: How to adjust insulin Humulin-I® if CBGs continue to be out of the treatment range 6-11 mmol/L.

To be used in conjunction with the King's gguidelines for maintaining blood glucose control in patients with COVID-19 given dexamethasone